

"Boomerang" Technology in Teaching the Subject "Disclosure of Uncertainty Using Production"

Rashidov Anvarjon Sharipovich

Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute, Associate Professor of the Department of Mathematics and Informatics

Rozmetova is Zuhrajon Muradbek's daughter

Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute, 3rd year student of mathematics and informatics education

Article information:

Manuscript received: 04 Aug 2024; **Accepted:** 04 Sep 2024; **Published:** 19 Oct 2024

Abstract: The article describes how to teach "Derivative" using Boomerang technology. Boomerang technology is convenient for the study of topics with different content and character (problematic, controversial, different meanings), including oral and written forms of work, and during one session each allows the participant to perform various tasks, in turn in the role of a student or teacher, to collect the required score, to teach students in the classroom, outside the classroom to work with different literature, texts, memorize the studied material, so ' to be able to express themselves freely and to evaluate all students during a lesson.

Keywords: Derivation, Uncertainty, Lopital, Boomerang technology, lesson, student, teacher, topic, assessment, group, teaching materials.

Currently, there are many types of training using advanced pedagogical technologies (interactive methods), which are selected and prepared according to the characteristics of the subject of the lesson and the intended goals. This is very important when passing math lessons. In this case, specific requirements are placed on the students' preparation. In particular: mastering the necessary knowledge for active participation in training, readiness for communication, working in mutual cooperation, independent thinking, skills to express and defend one's opinion freely, etc.

A sickle-shaped throwing weapon, which ensures that the thrown object returns to the thrower, is called a boomerang. The meaning of the boomerang method in education is that the problematic issue or topic raised by the pedagogue is returned to the teacher in oral or written form after being mastered by the students.

1. If there are 4 parts of topics in the lesson plan, students in the classroom are also divided into 4 groups. The first part of the plan is presented to each of the students of the first group with the answers prepared by the subject teacher. In this way, the other parts of the plan, together with their answers, will be distributed to the students of groups with appropriate numbers. Students in each group study one part of the topic presented to them with their answers according to the rules set by the teacher.

2. After that, students of 4 groups are mixed and 4 groups of new composition are formed. In each of these new groups, more than one student from each of the first 4 groups is achieved. As a result, there is an opportunity to study the entire educational material as a whole team.

It is important that students develop the skills and abilities to learn the educational material independently, work cooperatively, and explain what they know to others.

3. After completing the group study of the topic according to the rules set by the teacher, students return to their original groups and the question-and-answer session begins. Based on the organization of the teacher, questions are given to one team by other groups. One student chosen by them from the team writes down the scores of their partners, sums them up, and submits the results to the teacher. All groups will be quizzed in this way. 3 points are given to a student who answered the question correctly, 2 points to a correct addition, 1 point to a correct replica, and 0 points to a student who did not express an opinion at all.

4. Each group prepares one question on the topic and invites other groups to answer it. 3 points will be added to the total score of the team that answered correctly, and 0 points will be given to others. If no one can answer, if the team that created the question answers, 3 points will be added to their total score.

5. Now, to evaluate each student, pre-prepared test tasks on the subject are distributed to them. The results of the work of one group are checked by the students of the other group based on the prepared answers, and a score is given according to the scale provided by the teacher.

6. The lesson is strengthened and summarized by the teacher with the participation of students. Teams and students are announced and encouraged. Assignments and tasks needed for the next lesson are formed.

If there is a shortage of class time depending on the level of preparation of the students of the group, the size of the educational materials, ease or difficulty, the fourth stage may not be held.

Boomerang technology transfer steps

1 – stage. Group students are divided into small groups of 4-5 people;

- the teacher gives each group and each of its members specific handouts for independent learning, thinking and memorization. Their number depends on the number of groups and students. If there are 5 sub-groups, then the general topic is divided into 5 sub-texts and given to each group;
- for the activity to be effective, the text given to each group is given to each student. Thus, 5 groups will have 5 different texts based on a common theme, and each student will have a text in his group.

For example, “Revealing ambiguities using the derivative. Let's divide the topic "Hospital rule" into 5 parts and distribute it to small groups:

1. Ambiguities.
2. Rules for calculating the derivative.
3. Hospital rule.
4. Calculation of the derivative using the limit.
5. Uncertainties using the derivative.

2- stage. The teacher tells the group that the group members should study the text individually, memorize the text, and then, if necessary, tell it to others or the teacher, learn the text as much as possible, and for preparation, read the text in large or 10-15 minutes depending on the size. He himself observes the work of the group and students.

3-stage. The teacher comes to each group with small pieces of paper with pre-prepared numbers and asks the group members to draw one number from these pieces of paper (the

number of pieces of paper depends on the number of students in the group, for example, 5 in the group. If there is a person, the numbers on the paper are prepared as 1,2,3,4,5. few are prepared.

The teacher asks the students to form new groups by numbers. For example, everyone asks that those who received number 1 form one new group, those with number 2 form the second group, those with number 3 form the third group, those with number 4 form the fourth group, and those with number 5 form the fifth group. The members of the group take the texts they have learned with them to the new group.

4 – stage. When new groups are formed by numbers, one representative from the previous groups is automatically collected in each new group, that is, if 5 different texts are studied, one representative from each is collected in this new group, 5 students and 5 different texts are collected on a common topic.

5-stage. Each member of the newly formed group now takes on 2 tasks, i.e. teacher and student, and functions as follows:

- as a teacher (instructor), he talks about the material he has learned before, draws everyone's attention to the main points of the material he has learned independently, and checks the understanding and mastering abilities of other group members.
- as a student, he listens, analyzes, thinks and tries to remember the texts that the group members speak, explain and speak in turn.
- the teacher informs them that they should only speak their texts and gives them about 20 minutes (time is allocated depending on the size of the text and the difficulty or ease of the general topic).

At this stage, all the material distributed at the beginning of the training is considered to be mastered by the students.

6 – stage. After the members of the group have spoken their texts to each other, and after they have all learned these texts, the teacher asks the members of each group to each other to check how much the learned material has been mastered by the members of the group. z explains that they can ask questions based on the texts. Thus, internal control is carried out within the group, that is, through question-and-answer. This helps the students in the group to determine the degree of mastery of the materials they have shared with each other, and to further strengthen their own knowledge.

7 – stage. The teacher asks all the students to return to their previous places, that is, the students return to their groups at the beginning of the lesson.

8 – stage. The teacher says that all students in the classroom are familiar with the distributed written materials and that they have full knowledge about them, so they can ask each student about the studied material.

9 – stage. In order to determine the extent to which the distributed educational material has been mastered by the students, the teacher explains that he evaluates the students' answers to the control questions by rating points, for example, the answers to the questions - if there is a complete answer - 3 points, additional if it is done - 2 points, if a bite is thrown from the sitting place - 1 point, if there is no answer - 0 points will be assigned.

In the grading system, it is possible to assign 5 marks for a complete answer, 4 marks for an addition, 3 marks for missing a bite, and 2 marks for not answering.

In order to evaluate the answers of the group members in the order indicated above, each group can assign one of the group participants as a "scorekeeper" (the scorekeeper also participates in the question-and-answer dialogue in the circle).

10-stage. The teacher addresses the students with questions (5-6) based on the handouts (the questions should be relevant to all texts as much as possible, and the teacher tries to include all students in the classroom to answer).

Sample questions:

1. What is a derivative?
2. What is the algebraic form of the derivative formula of a complex function?
3. How to find the product of addition, subtraction, multiplication and division?
4. What are uncertainties?
5. How to open ambiguities using the derivative?
6. What is the hospital rule?
7. The geometric meaning of the derivative?
8. The physical meaning of the derivative?
9. Give the derivative of basic trigonometric functions.

After answering the set questions, the teacher writes the points collected by the groups on the board and moves on to the next stage of the exercise.

11 – stage. The teacher tells each group to prepare one question based on the content of their written materials, and gives the groups 5-7 minutes to prepare the question.

12 – stage. The groups ask each other questions, and the "calculators" in the groups evaluate the answers of the group members in the order specified above. If the answers are correct, the group that asked the question does not fill in the answer.

13 – stage. The teacher once again writes the points scored by the group members on the board and determines the total value of the points (grades). The total value of the accumulated points (grades) is divided equally among all group members (on the basis of agreement).

Note: if there is disagreement on the part of students in dividing the accumulated points equally among the group members, that is, some group members actively participated in the group's activities and were passive in the general collective activity, or if they did not participate at all, they were not interested, in such a case it is up to the group members to solve the situation. The group's solution is considered correct, or the teacher can express his opinion, as he observes the students' responses, active or passive, during the lesson.

In general, even if the student did not show activity, or did not participate in the questions and answers, he can be given the smallest score, taking into account that he has memorized something in the course of the lesson. This encourages the student to be more active in this type of lessons later. If a situation like the one above arises, each teacher can solve it himself, depending on the situation, or throw it to a group or team.

Sometimes a group's "scorekeepers" may make inaccuracies or overwrite the scores, resulting in some groups' total scores being very little different from those of other groups. The teacher mentions in advance that the students' true assessment depends on their chosen "accountants". If the total accumulated points, when distributed among the group members, exceed the maximum points set for this exercise, then the necessary points for this exercise can be deducted, and the excess can be transferred to the next exercises or the final control.

14-stage. After scoring each student, the teacher ends the lesson.

He evaluates the work of students, expresses his opinion on the given answers and addresses them with the following questions:

- ✓ What did you learn from today's training?
- ✓ what did you learn?
- ✓ What's new for you?
- ✓ what else would you like to know?

15-stage.The teacher listens carefully to the students' answers, thanks them and ends the lesson.

This technology is aimed at learning the educational material in a deep and integrated state during one session, creatively understanding it, and freely mastering it.

Using the technology presented in the article, it is possible to organize classes effectively [1-21]. It is recommended to use various modern pedagogical technologies in order to increase students' interest during the training session. The use of modern educational technologies not only increases students' interest in science, but also helps them acquire deep knowledge and skills.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR

1. Rasulov T., Kurbonov G. Effective use of digital learning technologies in the educational process. AIP Conf. Proc. 2901 (2023), 030007-1–030007-7.
2. Rasulov T., Umarova U. The role of modern information and communication technologies in the organization of distance education. AIP Conf. Proc. 2901 (2023), 030008-1–030007-10.
3. Rasulov T.H., Rashidov A.Sh. The usage of foreign experience in effective organization of teaching activities in Mathematics. International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research. 9:4 (2020), pp. 3068-3071.
4. A.Sh. Rashidov Ijtimoiy-gumanitar ta'lim yo'nalishi talabalari uchun matematik fanlar bo'yicha amaliy mashg'ulotlarni o'tkazish. Science and Education №9. С 283-291
5. О.О.Халлоқова. А.Рашидов Пороговое собственное значение модели Фридрихса. Молодой ученый, 2015 №15. С. 1-3
6. A. Sh. Rashidov Interaktivnyye metody pri izuchenii temy "Opredelenny integral i yego prilozheniya". Nauchnyye issledovaniya. № 34:3. С 21-24
7. A. Sh. Rashidov Yoshlar intellektual kamolotida ijodiy tafakkur va kreativlikning o'ri. Pedagogik mahorat 2021 yil №7. 114-116 bet.
8. A.Sh. Rashidov. Matematika fanlaridan talaba yoshlar ijodiy tafakkurini rivojlantirish. Fan va jamiyat №3. С 45-46
9. A.Sh. Rashidov замонавий таълим ва инновацион технологиялар соҳасидаги илғор тажрибалар. Центр научных публикаций. 2021 yil. 3-son. 68-72 bet 8-14
10. A.Sh.Rashidov. M.F.Faxridinova. O'quvchilarning bilimni baholashda xalqaro baholash dasturlari. "Fizika, matematika va informatsion texnologiyalarning innovatsion rivojlanishdagi o'ri" mavzusidagi Respublika ilmiy-nazariy anjuman. Buxoro. 222-227 bet.
11. A. Sh. Rashidov Matematika darslarida ta'limning shaxsga yo 'naltirilgan texnologiyasi. Центр научных публикаций. 2021 yil. 3-son. 68-72 bet
12. Jo'rayeva N. O., Hasanova M.F. Birhad va ko'phadni birhadga bo'lish. Образование и наука в XXI веке». Выпуск №26 (том 6) (май, 2022).632-644 стр
13. Jo'rayeva N. O., Образование и наука в XXI веке». Выпуск №26 (том 6) (май, 2022).

-620-631 стр

14. Jurayeva N.O. Fundamentals of Organizing Students' Independent Work Using Mobile Applications. *Child Studies in Asia-Pacific Context (CSAC)*. 2022, 12 (1); 255-266
15. Jurayeva N.O. Specific aspects and principles of the method of organizing independent education of students. *Actual problems of modern science, education and training*". №8, Xorazm, 2022. – P. 23-27. (13.00.00; № 24).
16. Jo'rayeva N.O. Mobile Softwareanwendungen zur Organisation unabhängiger Bildung// Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities. Vol. 2, Issue 1.5 (2022), – P. -661-664. (13.00.00; № 7).
17. Jo'rayeva N.O. Mustaqil ta'limni tashkil etishda mobil ilovalaridan foydalanish. Ta'lim va innovasion tadqiqotlar. 2023 год №1. -273-27 b
18. Qurbonov, G. U. (2022). O'quv jarayonlarida talabalar faolligini oshirish maqsadida mobil ilovalardan foydalanishning o'g'ni. *Инновационные исследования в современном мире: теория и практика*, 1(17), 21-23.
19. Ғафурович, Қ. Ғ. (2022). Smart education масофавий фан тўгараги ва уни ташкил этиш методикаси: <https://doi.org/10.53885/edinres>. 2022.8. 08.036. *Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал*, (8), 239-245.
20. G'afurovich, Q. G. U. (2024). Didactic possibilities of teaching the educational process on the base of digital educational technologies. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 309-313.
21. G'afurovich, Q. G. U. (2024). Interfaol usullar yordamida uchburchak tengsizligi mavzusini o'qitish metodikasi. *pedagog*, 7(5), 522-532.